
Jaíne S. Rebouças

Graduated in Agroecology from the Federal University of the Reconcavo of Bahia (UFRB) and holds a master's degree in Agricultural Sciences from the same institution. Currently, she is a doctoral student in the Graduate Program in Agricultural Sciences (CAPES scholarship) at UFRB and a member of the Insecta Research Group at the Center for Agricultural, Environmental, and Biological Sciences at UFRB. Has experience in the management of social bees (Meliponini) (Apini), Technical Assistance and Rural Extension (ATER), Ecology, and the toxicity of pesticides on non-target organisms (bees).

EFFECTS OF PESTICIDES ON *Nannotrigona testaceicornis* (IRAI BEE)

Jaíne S. Rebouças^{1,3*}, Maiara J. M. Caldas^{1,3}, Jefferson A. dos Santos^{1,3}, Joilson da C. Santana²; Erislan F. Santos², Maria A. P. de C. Costa^{1,3}, Ana T.B. Guimarães^{4,5}, Nuno G.C. Ferreira^{6,7} and Carlos A. L. de Carvalho^{1,3}

¹Postgraduate Program in Agricultural Sciences, Federal University of the Reconcavo of Bahia, Cruz das Almas-BA, 44380-000, Brazil

²Undergraduate Student in Agronomy, Federal University of the Reconcavo of Bahia, Cruz das Almas-BA, 44380-000, Brazil

³Insecta Research Group, Center for Agricultural, Environmental and Biological Sciences, Federal University of the Reconcavo of Bahia, Cruz das Almas-BA, 44380-000, Brazil

⁴Ecotoxicology and Landscape Research Group, Rua Universitária n. 1619, Cascavel-PR, Brazil

⁵Graduate Program of Bioscience and Health, UNIOESTE – Rua Universitária n. 2069, Cascavel-PR, Brazil

⁶CIIMAR - Interdisciplinary Centre of Marine and Environmental Research, Terminal de Cruzeiros do Porto de Leixões, Matosinhos, Portugal

⁷School of Biosciences- Cardiff University, Museum Avenue, Cardiff CF10 3AX, Wales-UK

* Corresponding author: jainedossantos27@gmail.com

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Abstract

Stingless bees are essential for maintaining ecosystems through the ecological service of pollination[1]. However, the damage caused by pesticides commonly used in agricultural areas represents a huge threat to bees' survival [2]. The objective of this work was to test the impact of three pesticides (λ -cyhalothrin, triflumizole, and fenpyroximate) through three routes of exposure (ingestion, topical, and contact surface) in the species *Nannotrigona testaceicornis* [3, 4, 5].

Bees were exposed to different concentrations of these pesticides, and lethal and sublethal effects were recorded after 1, 6, 12, 24, 48, 72 and 96 hours of exposure. To test whether pesticides cause mortality in bees upon acute exposure, survival curves were obtained with Kaplan–Meier estimators and were first analyzed using the log-rank test. Subsequently, pairwise comparisons were performed using the Benjamini-Hocheberg adjustment ($p < 0.05$). Analyses were performed using R software [6]. The insecticide λ -cyhalothrin caused a significant reduction in bee survival only through the topical route (survival $> 62,1\%$; $\chi^2= 25.6$, $df= 5$, $p = 0.0001$). As for the fungicide (triflumizole) and acaricide (fenpyroximate), no significant impact on the survival of bees was observed through the three exposure routes ($p > 0.05$). However, bees presented several behavioural changes, such as agitation, disorientation and difficulty in locomotion. The sublethal effect of paralysis was recorded only in topical exposures to λ -cyhalothrin. The results obtained from the exposures show that, although acute exposure does not cause significant mortality in bees, it promotes significant behavioural changes that directly impact bee's survival, increasing the possibility of predation and population decline. Therefore, the sublethal effects generated by pesticide exposure will directly impact bees, causing high mortality or indirectly through behavioural changes. This will cause a negative impact on ecosystem services provided by these key organisms.

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